

Neural Operator Based Surrogate Model for Neutron Transport Computation

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a neural operator based surrogate modeling framework for neutron transport computations. Two models, the Deep Operator Network (DeepONet) and the Fourier Neural Operator (FNO), were developed to learn the mapping between anisotropic neutron sources and the corresponding angular fluxes in a one-dimensional slab geometry. Both models produced accurate angular flux predictions across unseen source configurations, with the FNO achieving mean squared errors on the order of 10^{-8} to 10^{-7} while requiring less than 5% of the S_N solver runtime, and DeepONet achieving slightly higher errors ($\sim 10^{-6}$ in most cases) but faster inference ($< 3\%$ of the runtime). The models were further integrated into a k-eigenvalue solver to replace computationally intensive inner loop of solving a fixed-source problem by iterative transport sweeps. Both surrogate models reproduced the reference eigenvalues for two representative test cases: DeepONet yielded noticeable deviations of -1106 pcm and -740 pcm, while FNO achieved much smaller deviations of -46 pcm and -34 pcm. In terms of computational performance, DeepONet required approximately 1% of the computational time of the S_N solver, whereas FNO required about 6–8%. These results highlight the strong potential of neural operator frameworks as efficient and accurate surrogates for neutron transport, enabling real-time digital twin applications as well as rapid reactor and shielding analyses.

Keywords: DeepONet, FNO, Neutron Transport, Neural Operator, Surrogate Model

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate characterization of neutron behavior across spatial, angular, and energy domains is a cornerstone of reactor physics, forming the foundation for reactor design, shielding analysis, criticality safety, and multiphysics coupling applications. The governing framework for these phenomena is the neutron transport equation (NTE), whose numerical solution provides comprehensive insight into neutron interactions within the systems [1]. However, while existing deterministic and Monte Carlo solvers can deliver highly accurate results, their computational demands are substantial, posing challenges for tasks that require rapid or repeated evaluations, such as design optimization or uncertainty quantification. The demand for computational efficiency is even more pressing in digital twin environments, where real-time or near-real-time predictions are required to guide operational decisions [2]. Achieving high-fidelity solutions with reduced computational cost remains a persistent challenge in this domain. In recent years, deep learning method physics informed neural networks (PINNs) and its modified architecture have been explored for solving the NTE and related transport problems [3–5]. Although these approaches have shown potential, they generally exhibit poor generalization when system parameters such as material properties or boundary conditions change. Both conventional machine learning techniques and traditional numerical solvers are usually formulated for fixed physical settings – parameters describing neutron emissions/interactions or initial/boundary conditions [6]; therefore, each variation in physical settings necessitates either a new simulation or complete retraining of the model, resulting in high computational overhead and limited flexibility.

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Neural operator frameworks have emerged as compelling solutions for developing efficient surrogate models for partial differential equations (PDEs) [7]. Architectures such as the Deep Operator Network (DeepONet) [8] and the Fourier Neural Operator (FNO) [9] have shown remarkable success in learning solution operators that directly map input functions to corresponding output functions in infinite-dimensional spaces. Unlike standard neural networks, which learn discrete, pointwise relationships, neural operators learn continuous function to function mappings, allowing them to capture the governing physics of a system holistically. This enables strong generalization across unseen conditions without the need for retraining, making them ideal for repetitive evaluations as well as for parameter-varying physical problems. DeepONet and its variants have been successfully employed in diverse scientific and engineering domains such as material fracture prediction [10], thermal transport modeling [11] and complex multiphysics simulations [12]. Similarly, the Fourier Neural Operator (FNO) and its extensions have demonstrated strong performance in simulating multiphase flow dynamics [13], and modeling fusion plasma behavior [14]. However, their application to solve NTE is limited in literature [15-18]. In our prior works [15-17], we employed a neural operator approach to construct a surrogate model for the NTE that mapped an isotropic neutron source $S(x)$ to the resulting scalar flux $\phi(x)$. In the present study, we extend this framework to the more general anisotropic transport problem by developing neural operator based surrogate models that learn the mapping between the anisotropic source $Q(x, \mu)$ and the corresponding angular flux $\psi(x, \mu)$. Using data generated from high-fidelity NTE simulations for fixed macroscopic cross sections, both DeepONet and FNO architectures are trained to approximate the underlying transport operator. Once trained, these models provide rapid and accurate evaluations of the angular flux and can be further integrated into eigenvalue formulations, enabling efficient, generalizable, and high-fidelity neutron flux predictions across a wide range of source conditions.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Fixed Source NTE

The present study focuses on solving the fixed-source neutron transport problem within a one-dimensional slab geometry, as shown in Figure 1. The slab extends 10 cm in length and is bounded on both sides by vacuum (zero incoming current) boundary conditions. Material properties, namely, absorption, scattering, and total cross sections, are considered spatially uniform across the domain, and an internal source distribution is defined within the slab.

Figure 1. 1D Slab considered for the fixed source NTE.

The steady-state one-group neutron transport equation for the one-dimensional slab geometry is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu \frac{\partial \psi(x, \mu)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_t \psi(x, \mu) &= \int_{-1}^1 \frac{1}{2} [\Sigma_{s0} + 3\mu\mu' \Sigma_{s1}] \psi(x, \mu') d\mu' + Q(x, \mu); \\ 0 < x < X, \quad -1 \leq \mu \leq 1 \\ \psi(0, \mu) &= 0, \quad 0 \leq \mu \leq 1 \\ \psi(X, \mu) &= 0, \quad -1 \leq \mu \leq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In this context, μ represents the cosine of the scattering angle, $\psi(x, \mu)$ denotes the angular neutron flux, Σ_t is the total cross section, Σ_{S0} and Σ_{S1} are the zeroth and first Legendre moments of the scattering cross section, and $Q(x, \mu)$ corresponds to the internal neutron source. The left-hand side of the equation accounts for neutron loss, whereas the right-hand side includes contributions from in-scattering and the internal source. For fixed cross sections (Σ_t , Σ_{S0} and Σ_{S1}), different internal sources $Q(x, \mu)$ result in varying angular fluxes $\psi(x, \mu)$. The aim of this study is to develop a neural operator based surrogate model capable of mapping $Q(x, \mu)$ to the corresponding $\psi(x, \mu)$, providing fast and highly accurate predictions. To accomplish this, DeepONet and FNO architectures were trained on datasets containing a wide range of internal source distributions along with their associated angular flux solutions.

2.2. Deep Operator Network (DeepONet)

DeepONet leverages the Universal Approximation Theorem for Operators [8, 19], which guarantees that neural networks can approximate nonlinear operators acting on functions. It models the operator G mapping a source function $Q(x, \mu)$ to the angular flux $\psi(x, \mu)$ using two coupled networks: BranchNet and TrunkNet. The BranchNet encodes the discretized source into a latent vector $\mathbf{b}_N = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_p]$, while the TrunkNet maps query coordinates (x, μ) into a mode vector $\mathbf{t}_N = [t_1(x, \mu), t_2(x, \mu), \dots, t_p(x, \mu)]$ (Figure 2). The predicted flux is obtained as their inner product:

$$\psi(x, \mu) \approx \mathbf{b}_N \cdot \mathbf{t}_N^T = \sum_{i=1}^p b_i t_i(x, \mu) \quad (2)$$

This architecture enables DeepONet to learn the operator efficiently, allowing rapid and accurate flux predictions for unseen source profiles across arbitrary spatial and angular locations, supporting real-time neutron transport analysis.

Figure 2. Architecture of DeepONet.

2.3. Fourier Neural Operator (FNO)

The FNO offers a data-driven framework for approximating solution operators of partial differential equations [9]. In this work, the FNO is trained to predict the angular flux $\psi(x, \mu)$ from the internal source $Q(x, \mu)$. The discretized source is first embedded into a higher-dimensional latent space using a shallow fully connected network, yielding \tilde{Q} which is then processed through a series of Fourier layers (Figure 3). Each Fourier layer first applies an FFT to transfer the input into Fourier space, then uses a learnable linear layer to map the Fourier coefficients (to solution space), after which high-frequency modes may be truncated. The data is then transformed back to the spatial domain via an inverse FFT. The FFT/IFFT are fixed computations; the linear mapping is the only learnable component of the layer. In parallel, a pointwise linear transformation is applied directly in the spatial domain, and the results from both paths are combined with a nonlinear activation. After F such layers, the final representation \tilde{Q}_F is projected back to the target dimension to produce $\psi(x, \mu)$. The FNO is capable of zero-shot super-

resolution, meaning that a model trained on low-resolution data can be directly evaluated on higher-resolution inputs without retraining [9].

Figure 3. Architecture of FNO.

2.4. Model Training

To train the DeepONet and FNO models, datasets were generated by numerically solving Eq. (1) with discretization in both space and angle. The spatial domain was divided into J uniformly spaced cells of width $h_j = 0.1 \text{ cm}$, using a cell-averaged finite difference scheme for spatial discretization [1]. The edges of the j^{th} cell are denoted $x_{j\pm\frac{1}{2}}$ with the cell width h_j and center x_j defined in Eq. (3).

$$h_j = x_{j+\frac{1}{2}} - x_{j-\frac{1}{2}} \text{ and } x_j = \frac{1}{2} \left(x_{j+\frac{1}{2}} + x_{j-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The cell averaged value p_j of a function $p(x)$ over the j^{th} cell is then given by

$$p_j = \frac{1}{h_j} \int_{x_{j-\frac{1}{2}}}^{x_{j+\frac{1}{2}}} p(x) dx \quad (4)$$

For the angular discretization, the discrete ordinates (S_N) method [1] was employed, using Gauss-Legendre quadrature with $N = 16$ angular bins. Applying both spatial and angular discretization, Eq. (1) can then be expressed in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_n}{h_j} \left(\psi_{n,j+\frac{1}{2}} - \psi_{n,j-\frac{1}{2}} \right) + \Sigma_{tj} \psi_{n,j} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\Sigma_{S0,j} \varphi_{0,j} + 3\mu_n \Sigma_{S1,j} \varphi_{1,j} + Q_{n,j} \right) \\ 1 \leq n \leq N, 1 \leq j \leq J \\ \psi_{n,\frac{1}{2}} &= 0, \frac{N}{2} + 1 \leq n \leq N, \mu_n > 0 \\ \psi_{n,J+\frac{1}{2}} &= 0, 1 \leq n \leq \frac{N}{2}, \mu_n < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Here, n and j denote the angular bin and spatial cell indices, respectively. μ_n is the cosine of the scattering angle for the n^{th} direction, while $\psi_{n,j+\frac{1}{2}}$ and $\psi_{n,j-\frac{1}{2}}$ denote the angular flux at the right and left edges of the j^{th} cell. The total cross section is Σ_{tj} , and the cell-averaged angular flux $\psi_{n,j}$ is defined in Eq. (4). The zeroth and first Legendre moments of the scattering cross section are $\Sigma_{S0,j}$ and $\Sigma_{S1,j}$, respectively.

$$\varphi_{0,j} = \sum_{n=1}^N \psi_{n,j} w_n \quad (6)$$

$$\varphi_{1,j} = \sum_{n=1}^N \psi_{n,j} \mu_n w_n \quad (7)$$

Scalar flux $\varphi_{0,j}$ and current $\varphi_{1,j}$ are defined in Eqs. (6) and (7), where w_n is the Gauss–Legendre quadrature weight, and $Q_{n,j}$ is the internal source for the n^{th} direction in cell j . The relationship between cell-edge and cell-averaged angular fluxes is expressed using the diamond difference approximation [1]:

$$\psi_{n,j} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\psi_{n,j+\frac{1}{2}} + \psi_{n,j-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (8)$$

Using the prescribed source term $Q_{n,j}$, Eq. (5) was solved to obtain the cell-averaged angular flux $\psi_{n,j}$. The sources $Q_{n,j}$ were generated from Gaussian Random Fields (GRFs) and employed in the numerical solution of the fixed source NTE to produce the corresponding angular flux $\psi_{n,j}$. To train the DeepONet and FNO models, paired datasets of the anisotropic source $Q(x, \mu)$ and the resulting angular flux $\psi(x, \mu)$ were generated. For improved scalability, the source term is often normalized so that the total source represents a single neutron distributed across the whole domain. Now, the total source emission density $S(x)$ at x can be obtained by integrating $Q(x, \mu)$ over angles:

$$S(x) = \int_{-1}^1 Q(x, \mu) d\mu, \text{ with } S_{total} = \int_0^x S(x) dx \quad (9)$$

In discrete form:

$$S_j = \sum_{n=1}^N Q_{n,j} w_n, \quad 1 \leq n \leq N \text{ and } S_{total} = \sum_{j=1}^J S_j h_j, \quad 1 \leq j \leq J \quad (10)$$

Initially, 1000 GRF samples of $S(x)$ with mean (M) 0.07, variance (σ^2) 0.0003, and length scale (l) 1.2 were generated over 100 spatial points ($h_j = 0.1$ cm) and normalized according to

$$S_{j,nor} = \frac{S_j}{\sum_{j=1}^{100} S_j h_j}, \text{ such that } \sum_{j=1}^{100} S_{j,nor} h_j = 1 \quad (11)$$

For each, $S_{j,nor}$, an angle-dependent GRF $Q'(x, \mu)$ ($M = 0.5$, $\sigma^2 = 0.02$, $l = 6.0$) was generated with 16 angular bins. The angular sources were then normalized according to

$$Q_{n,j} = Q'_{n,j} \left(\frac{S_{j,nor}}{\sum_{n=1}^{16} Q'_{n,j} w_n} \right) \quad (12)$$

ensuring that the consistency condition

$$S_{j,nor} = \sum_{n=1}^{16} Q_{n,j} w_n \quad (13)$$

is satisfied with all spatial points j . These $Q_{n,j}$ served as inputs, with $\psi_{n,j}$ from numerical NTE solutions as targets. The training dataset was created using a single set of cross-section values: $\Sigma_t = 1.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Sigma_{s0} = 0.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\Sigma_{s1} = 0.25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These input-output pairs were then used to train the DeepONet and FNO neural operator models. Both models were implemented in PyTorch [20] and trained using the Adam optimizer with mean squared error (MSE) loss on a workstation with an NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU and Intel i9-14900KS CPU. DeepONet's BranchNet had layers [1600, 1200, 800, 600, 400, 200] and TrunkNet [2, 200, 200, 200, 200, 200], with ReLU activations. Training for 1500 epochs (~ 50 hours) converged to a loss of $\sim 10^{-7}$. FNO inputs included discretized sources and spatial-angular coordinates,

lifted to a 64-dimensional latent space, processed through two Fourier layers with 24 spatial and 8 angular modes, and projected back to the grid. ReLU activations were applied, and training completed in ~400 seconds over 2000 epochs, achieving a final loss of $\sim 10^{-7}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fixed Source Problem

To evaluate the generalization performance and computational efficiency of the DeepONet and FNO model, six distinct test cases were constructed in the same process described in section 2.4 by varying ℓ of $S(x)$ and $Q'(x, \mu)$. One hundred random test samples were generated for each configuration, and both models were tested using these inputs. The average of the sample-wise MSE between the predicted and reference angular fluxes was computed to quantify accuracy. Additionally, the average inference time of each model was recorded and expressed as a percentage of the runtime of the traditional S_N solver, thereby enabling a direct assessment of computational efficiency. The results of these evaluations are summarized in Table I.

Table I. Results of the Fixed Source Problem.

Cases	Average MSE		Runtime (% of S_N Solver)	
	FNO	DeepONet	FNO	DeepONet
Case 1 [$S(x): l = 1.2; Q'(x, \mu): l = 6.0$]	9.68×10^{-8}	8.04×10^{-6}	4.08	2.92
Case 2 [$S(x): l = 1.2; Q'(x, \mu): l = 4.0$]	3.33×10^{-7}	9.04×10^{-6}	4.34	3.06
Case 3 [$S(x): l = 1.2; Q'(x, \mu): l = 8.0$]	6.75×10^{-8}	7.84×10^{-6}	3.81	2.81
Case 4 [$S(x): l = 1.0; Q'(x, \mu): l = 6.0$]	8.12×10^{-8}	1.04×10^{-5}	4.20	2.94
Case 5 [$S(x): l = 1.4; Q'(x, \mu): l = 6.0$]	9.67×10^{-8}	6.99×10^{-6}	4.40	2.89
Case 6 [$S(x): l = 1.4; Q'(x, \mu): l = 4.0$]	3.25×10^{-7}	7.99×10^{-6}	4.47	3.00

As shown in Table I, both DeepONet and FNO demonstrated strong predictive accuracy across all test cases, with MSE values on the order of 10^{-6} – 10^{-8} in most cases. The FNO consistently achieved lower MSE values than DeepONet, indicating superior generalization to unseen source configurations. For instance, in Case 1, FNO achieved an average MSE of 9.68×10^{-8} compared to 8.04×10^{-6} for DeepONet. Similar performance trends were observed across other cases, confirming the robustness of the spectral-based FNO representation in capturing spatial and angular correlations. In terms of computational efficiency, both models exhibited significant acceleration compared to the S_N solver, requiring less than 5% of its runtime. Specifically, DeepONet demonstrated slightly faster inference, averaging around 3% of the solver time, while FNO averaged about 4%. Overall, these results highlight that both neural operator approaches provide accurate and efficient surrogates for the fixed source NTE, with FNO excelling in accuracy and DeepONet offering marginally faster evaluation speed.

3.2 Application to Eigenvalue NTE

In conventional approaches to solving the k-eigenvalue NTE, the inner iteration loop, responsible for solving a fixed-source problem by iterative transport sweeps, is the most computationally demanding step. This loop repeatedly solves a fixed source NTE to update the scalar flux using the current estimate of the fission source. To accelerate this process, we propose replacing the inner iteration loop with the DeepONet or FNO model previously trained for fixed source problems. These neural operators learn the mapping from the neutron source distribution to the corresponding angular flux, eliminating the need for repeated transport sweeps. During each power iteration, the DeepONet/FNO rapidly predicts the angular flux from the current source, thus avoiding the expensive transport solve. The predicted flux is then used to update both the fission source and the eigenvalue estimate, and the process repeats until convergence, substantially reducing the overall computational cost. For the eigenvalue problem, the same one-dimensional slab geometry and cross-section parameters were used as in the fixed-source case, with $\Sigma_t = 1.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Sigma_{s0} = 0.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\Sigma_{s1} = 0.25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, in this case, the internal source term was replaced by a fission source. The fission source $S_f(x)$ is defined as

$$S_f(x) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\vartheta \Sigma_f}{k} \int_{-1}^1 \psi(x, \mu') d\mu' \quad (14)$$

Here, Σ_f is the fission cross section, ϑ and k denote the average number of neutrons emitted per fission and eigenvalue, respectively. Two cases were analyzed, each corresponding to a different fission cross section (Case 1: $\Sigma_f = 0.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Case 2: $\Sigma_f = 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with $\vartheta = 2.6$ for each case), and the results obtained using the DeepONet and FNO based solvers were compared with those from the traditional S_N transport solver. The same convergence criteria of 10^{-5} were applied to both the eigenvalue and scalar flux within the power iteration loop for all three approaches.

Table II. Results of Eigenvalue Problem.

Cases	k_{eff}		Δk_{eff} (pcm)		Runtime (% of S_N Solver)		
	Traditional S_N Solver	DeepONet Based Solver	FNO Based Solver	DeepONet Based Solver	FNO Based Solver	DeepONet Based Solver	FNO Based Solver
Case 1	1.46997	1.45891	1.46951	-1106.0	-46.0	1.08	7.72
Case 2	0.98001	0.97261	0.97967	-740.0	-34.0	0.95	6.33

Table II summarizes the results of the k -eigenvalue problem for the two test cases. For Case 1, the DeepONet based solver predicted $k_{eff} = 1.45891$, corresponding to a deviation of -1106 pcm from the reference S_N result, while the FNO based solver achieved $k_{eff} = 1.46951$ with only -46 pcm deviation. Similarly, for Case 2, the DeepONet and FNO based solvers yielded deviations of -740 pcm and -34 pcm, respectively. Thus, the FNO model demonstrated notably higher accuracy for eigenvalue problem than the DeepONet model developed in this work. In terms of computational performance, the DeepONet based solver required only around 1% of the runtime relative to the traditional S_N solver, while the FNO solver required about 6–8% of the time. These results highlight the potential of neural operator based approaches to dramatically accelerate eigenvalue transport calculations while maintaining acceptable accuracy.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Neural operator (DeepONet and FNO) based surrogate models were successfully developed and applied to both fixed source and k -eigenvalue neutron transport problems. The results show that these models can accurately reproduce angular flux while offering significant computational speedups compared to traditional S_N solvers. The FNO consistently exhibited superior accuracy, capturing spatial and angular correlations more effectively, whereas DeepONet provided slightly faster inference. When incorporated into eigenvalue calculations, both neural operator solvers substantially reduced runtime. However, the FNO model maintains good agreement with the reference solutions, whereas the DeepONet model exhibits a higher discrepancy. Training with other datasets and further hyperparameter tuning could be explored to improve the accuracy of the DeepONet model. Overall, this study demonstrates the strong potential of neural operators as generalizable, and efficient alternatives to conventional neutron transport solvers, paving the way for real-time digital twin applications and rapid reactor and shielding design analyses. Since current models are limited to the cross section parameters they were trained on, future work will focus on developing approaches to solve the NTE that enables a single model to generalize across a wide range of cross section values.

REFERENCES

- [1]. E. E. Lewis & W. F. Miller. *Computational Methods of Neutron Transport*. John Wiley & Sons (1984).
- [2]. B. Kochunas and X. Huan. "Digital Twin Concepts with Uncertainty for Nuclear Power Applications", *Energies*, **14**, 4235, (2021).

- [3]. Y. Xie, Y. Wang, and Y. Ma. "Boundary Dependent Physics-Informed Neural Network for Solving Neutron Transport Equation", *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **195**, 110181 (2024).
- [4]. Q. A. Huhn, M. E. Tano, and J. C. Ragusa. "Physics-Informed Neural Network with Fourier Features for Radiation Transport in Heterogeneous Media", *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **197**, 9, 2484 (2023).
- [5]. M. H. Elhareef and Z. Wu. "Physics-Informed Neural Network Method and Application to Nuclear Reactor Calculations: A Pilot Study", *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **197**, 4, 601 (2022).
- [6]. J. He et al. "Sequential Deep Operator Networks (S-DeepONet) for Predicting Full-Field Solutions Under Time-Dependent Loads", *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, **127**, 107258, (2024).
- [7]. K. Azizzadenesheli, N. Kovachki, Z. Li, M. Liu-Schiaffini, J. Kossaifi, and A. Anandkumar. "Neural operators for accelerating scientific simulations and design", *Nat. Rev. Phys*, **6**, pp. 320-328 (2024).
- [8]. L. Lu, P. Jin, G. Pang, Z. Zhang, and G. E. Karniadakis. "Learning nonlinear operators via DeepONet based on the universal approximation theorem of operators", *Nature Machine Intelligence*, **3**, pp. 218-229 (2021).
- [9]. Z. Li, N. Kovachki, K. Azizzadenesheli, B. Liu, and K. Bhattacharya, A. Stuart, and A. Anandkumar. "Fourier Neural Operator for Parametric Partial Differential Equations", *International Conference on Learning Representations*, (2021).
- [10]. S. Goswami, M. Yin, Y. Yu, and G. E. Karniadakis. "A physics-informed variational DeepONet for predicting crack path in quasi-brittle materials", *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, **391**, 114587 (2022).
- [11]. Q. Cheng, M. H. Sahadath, H. Yang, S. Pan, and W. Ji. "Surrogate Modeling of Heat Transfer under Flow Fluctuation Conditions using Fourier Basis-Deep Operator Network with Uncertainty Quantification", *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **188**, 105895 (2025).
- [12]. M. Yaseen et al., "Fast and Accurate Reduced-Order Modeling of a MOOSE-Based Additive Manufacturing Model with Operator Learning", *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, **129**, p.3123–3139, (2023).
- [13]. G. Wen, Z. Li, K. Azizzadenesheli, A. Anandkumar, and S. M. Benson, U-FNO. "An enhanced Fourier neural operator-based deep-learning model for multiphase flow", *Advances in Water Resources*, **163**, 104180 (2022).
- [14]. V. Gopakumar, S. Pamela, L. Zanisi, and et. al. "Plasma surrogate modelling using Fourier neural operators", *Nuclear Fusion*, **64**, 056025 (2024).
- [15]. M. H. Sahadath, Q. Cheng, S. Pan, and W. Ji. "Deep Operator Network Based Surrogate Model for Neutron Transport Computation", *Proceedings of International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science & Engineering (M&C2025)*, Denver CO, USA, April 27-30, 2025.
- [16]. M. H. Sahadath, Q. Cheng, S. Pan, and W. Ji. "Characterization of DeepONet Performance for Neutron Transport Modeling", accept, *Nuclear Science and Engineering* (2025).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2025.2586955>
- [17]. Q. Cheng, M. H. Sahadath, H. Yang, S. Pan, and W. Ji. "Accelerating PDE Solvers with Equation-Recast Neural Operator Preconditioning", arXiv:2509.01416, (2025).
- [18]. J. K. Patel, M. C. Schmidt, A. Magliari, and T. A. Wareing. "Assessing AI-Enhanced Single-Sweep Approximations for Problems with Forward-Peaked Scattering in Slab Geometry", arXiv:2411.11858 (2024).
- [19]. T. Chen, and H. Chen. "Universal Approximation to Nonlinear Operators by Neural Networks with Arbitrary Activation Functions and its Application to Dynamical Systems", *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw*, **6**, p.911–917 (1995).
- [20]. A. Paszke, et al. "PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High Performance Deep Learning Library in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32", *Curran Associates, Inc.*, p. 8024-8035, (2019).